

Solution equilibria of some quaternary metal complexes involving iminodiacetic acid and L-pyrrolidine-2-carboxylic acid

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Abstract Equilibrium based computer studies on quaternary complex systems, viz $Mn^{II}/Co^{II}/Pb^{II}$ iminodiacetic acid (IMDA = A^{2-}) and L-pyrrolidine-2-carboxylic acid (proline = B^-) systems demonstrate the formation of mixed-metal mixed-ligand complexes of stoichiometry M^1M^2AB and $M^1M^2A_2B$ in addition to MAB , M_2A_2B , MA and MB complexes for all metal ions. Formation constants of the complexes at $35 \pm 1^\circ C$ and at fixed ionic strength, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ ($NaNO_3$) were evaluated using SCOGS computer program and the complex formation equilibria were elucidated with the aid of speciation curves. Stability order of metal complexes and solution structure of heteronuclear M_1M^2AB complexes have been discussed.

Keywords Solution equilibria, quaternary metal complex, iminodiacetic acid

In continuation to our recent communication¹ on multi-metal multi-ligand complexes, we report here the solution equilibria of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} and Pb^{II} metal ions with IMDA and proline ligands using pH-metry in aqueous medium. The relevant stability constants have been evaluated using SCOGS computer program. The stability constants of binary, ternary and quaternary complexes are determined at $35 \pm 1^\circ C$ and $I = 0.1 M$ ($NaNO_3$).

Results and discussion

The complex formation between M^{2+} metal ion and IMDA (A^{2-}), a tridentate ligand², involve N-imino and O-carboxylato atoms. Proline serves as a bidentate ligand. The pK values of the ligands and hydrolytic constants of M^{2+} (aq) ions are shown in Table 1. The overall stability constants of the metal complexes are listed in Table 2.

Table 1 Proton ligand and hydrolytic constants in aqueous solution

$T_{\text{comp}} = 35 \pm 1^\circ C$, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ ($NaNO_3$)

(a) Proton ligand constants ($\log \beta_{\text{proton}}$)

	<i>p</i>	<i>q</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>t</i>	$\log \beta_{\text{proton}}$
H ₃ A	0	0	1	0	-3	14.26
H ₂ A	0	0	1	0	-2	12.03
HA	0	0	1	0	-1	8.80
H ₂ B	0	0	0	1	-2	12.79
HB	0	0	0	1	-1	9.37

(b) Hydrolytic constants of M^{2+} (aq) ions ($\log \beta_{\text{hydrolytic}}$)

					Mn	Co	Pb
M(OH)	1	0	0	0	1	-	-10.50
							-7.90

Table 2 Metal ligand binary, ternary and quaternary constants in aqueous solutions

Temp = $35 \pm 1^\circ C$, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ ($NaNO_3$)

Standard deviations $\sim (\pm 0.1-0.5)$ in log scale

(a) Metal ligand constants ($\log \beta_{\text{proton}}$) binary systems

	<i>p</i>	<i>q</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>t</i>	Mn	Co	Pb
MA	1	0	1	0	0	5.35	7.00	7.57
MA ₂	1	0	2	0	0	9.89	13.87	14.86
MB	1	0	0	1	0	4.90	5.75	6.64

(b) Metal ligand constants ($\log \beta_{\text{proton}}$) ternary systems

						Mn	Co	Pb
MAB	1	0	1	1	0	11.23	12.65	13.89
M ₂ A ₂ B	2	0	2	1	0	27.78	28.89	29.40

(c) Metal ligand constants ($\log \beta_{\text{proton}}$) quaternary systems

						Pb-Mn	Pb-Co	Co-Mn
M ¹ M ² AB	1	1	1	1	0	22.20	23.00	22.12
M ¹ M ² A ₂ B	1	1	2	1	0	29.10	29.66	28.48

Mononuclear metal complexes Species present in the complexation equilibria of binary, $M^{2+} A^{2-}$ (1/1/1/2) systems are H_3A , H_2A , HA , MA , MA_2 and M^{2+} . Likewise in the $M^{2+} B^-$ (1/1) systems, species of the type, H_2B , HB , MB and M^{2+} exist. However, metal hydroxo species is also reported in case of PbB system. Ternary species, MAB is detected in the mononuclear ternary $M^{2+} A^{2-} B^-$ (1/1/1) system, along with the mononuclear binary species discussed above. Speciation curves indicate its formation according to following equilibria in the pH region = >4

Note

Fig. 1. Speciation curves of the complexes in $M(II)$ - IMDA - proline (2 : 2 : 1) systems (a) $M(II) = Mn^{II}$, (1) H_3A , (2) H_2A , (3) HA , (4) H_2B , (5) HB , (6) MnA , (7) MnB , (8) MnA_2 , (9) $MnAB$, (10) MnA_2B , (11) Mn_2A_2B , (b) $M(II) = Co^{II}$, (1) H_3A , (2) H_2A , (3) HA , (4) H_2B , (5) HB , (6) $Co(OH)^+$, (7) CoA , (8) CoB , (9) CoA_2 , (10) $CoAB$, (11) CoA_2B , (12) Co_2A_2B , (c) $M(II) = Pb^{II}$, (1) H_3A , (2) H_2A , (3) HA , (4) H_2B , (5) HB , (6) $Pb(OH)^+$, (7) PbA , (8) PbB , (9) PbA_2 , (10) $PbAB$, (11) PbA_2B , (12) Pb_2A_2B

In all of the systems concentration of free proline is more than that of IMDA, indicating stronger metal-ligand complexation in case of later.

Binuclear metal complexes : In homobinuclear ternary $M^{2+} : A^{2-} : B^-$ (2 : 2 : 1) systems, the only species present other than protonated ligand species is M_2A_2B . It shows its first appearance in acidic medium and exist throughout en-

Fig. 2. Speciation curves of the complexes in $M^I \cdot M^2 \cdot \text{IMDA} : \text{proline} (1 : 1 : 2 : 1)$ systems : (a) $M^I = \text{Pb}^{II}, M^2 = \text{Co}^{II}$, (1) H_3A , (2) H_2A , (3) HA , (4) H_2B , (5) HB , (6) $\text{Pb}(\text{OH})^+$, (7) $\text{Co}(\text{OH})^+$, (8) PbA , (9) PbA_2 , (10) ..., (11) CoA , (12) PbB , (13) CoB , (14) PbAB , (15) PbA_2B , (16) CoAB , (17) CoA_2B , (18) PbCoAB , (19) PbCoA_2B ; (b) $M^I = \text{Co}^{II}, M^2 = \text{Mn}^{II}$, (1) H_3A , (2) H_2A , (3) HA , (4) H_2B , (5) HB , (6) $\text{Co}(\text{OH})^+$, (7) CoA , (8) CoA_2 , (9) MnA , (10) MnA_2 , (11) CoB , (12) MnB , (13) CoAB , (14) CoA_2B , (15) MnAB , (16) MnA_2B , (17) CoMnAB , (18) CoMnA_2B ; (c) $M^I = \text{Pb}^{II}, M^2 = \text{Mn}^{II}$, (1) H_3A , (2) H_2A , (3) HA , (4) H_2B , (5) HB , (6) $\text{Pb}(\text{OH})^+$, (7) PbA , (8) PbA_2 , (9) MnAB , (10) MnA_2 , (11) PbB , (12) MnB , (13) PbAB , (14) PbA_2B , (15) MnAB , (16) MnA_2 , (17) PbMnAB , (18) PbMnA_2B .

the pH range. The formation of homobinuclear species (pH ~2.5–8) takes place according to following equilibrium :

In heterobinuclear quaternary $(M^1)^{2+} : (M^2)^{2+} : A^{2-} : B^- (1 : 1 : 1 : 1)$ systems, the complex species reported in appreciable concentration is M^1M^2AB . However, negligible

Note

amount of PbA is also found to exist in PbMnAB system. Formation of quaternary M^1M^2AB species in the pH range ~2.5–8 may be explained by the following equilibrium :

Since IMDA has more coordination positions available for binding a given bipoisitive metal ion as compared to the proline ligand, the stability constant for the formation of metal ligand bond in case of IMDA is greater than for the proline. Metal having higher $\log \beta$ value of metal-IMDA complex will be the first to attach with IMDA by carboxylate O-atoms on the equatorial plane. The imino N-atom however coordinates axially, thus IMDA coordinates with first metal ion in a tridentate manner^{3,4}.

In heterobinuclear $(M^1)^{2+} : (M^2)^{2+} : A^{2-} : B^-$ (1 : 1 : 2 : 1) quaternary system, M^1M^2AB and $M^1M^2A_2B$ species are predominantly present between pH ~2.5 and 8.5. Where, percentage concentration of M^1M^2AB species decreases down to negligible amount after attaining maximum value (~70–80%) at pH ~3.5–4 and species $M^1M^2A_2B$ reaches steadily to maximum extent ~95% at pH ~8. Distribution curves clearly indicate that formation of M^1M^2AB species take place in acidic medium whereas, $M^1M^2A_2B$ species is stable at higher pH.

Probable equilibria of formation of $M^1M^2A_2B$ complex in the given pH range can be proposed as given below :

Stability constants of binary MA, MB and ternary MAB, M_2A_2B complexes (Table 2) fall in the order $Pb > Co > Mn$, where, Co and Mn follow Irving-Williams order^{5,6}. Stability constants of quaternary complexes are found to be in general order : $Pb-Co > Pb-Mn > Co-Mn$.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of reagent grade. Their standard solutions were prepared by using doubly distilled CO_2 -free water. Metal salts were standardized by complexometric EDTA titration method⁷. pH measurements were made

with century model CP901-S pH meter using a special glass electrode (accuracy ± 0.01 pH) at 35 ± 1 °C.

Metal ligand mixture of following compositions were prepared for titration, keeping total volume 50 ml in each case (strength of metal and ligand in 50 ml = 0.001 M) ($I = 0.1$ M $NaNO_3$).

(i) M : A or B 1 : 1 and 1 : 2, binary mixtures, (ii) M : A : B 1 : 1 : 1 and 2 : 2 : 1 ternary mixtures, (iii) $M^1 : M^2 : A : B$ 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 and 1 : 1 : 2 : 1 quaternary mixtures. Where M, M^1 , M^2 are Mn^{II} , Co^{II} and Pb^{II} as required.

Procedure for pH-titrations was the same as described earlier⁸. Ionic product of water (K_w) and activity coefficient of hydrogen ion under the experimental conditions were obtained from literature⁹. Metal-ligand formation constants have been evaluated by SCOGS computer program¹⁰. Values of constant were supplied to the computer as input data to obtain distribution curves of the complexes occurring at different pH. Few representative curves are shown in Figs.1–2.

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